

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D4.1

Report on trust model for partner sites, and between sites and controlled-access researchers

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1. Executive Summary

In this deliverable document, we report on the activities for Deliverable 4.1 - Report on trust model for partner sites, and between sites and controlled-access researchers. The Work Package 4 (WP4) goals concern the development of a set of tools that can facilitate federated analyses of new and diverse genetic and genomic datasets, based on specific use cases. The tools selected will be using the common federated infrastructure established in WP1 and WP2, and the datasets will be described with metadata standards identified in WP3.

This work has contributed towards establishing a description of the trust model and four different levels of data access concerning specific cohort's data, identifying use cases for the development of federated analysis workflows and describing existing data access models to inspire subsequent WP4 deliverables related to the implementation of the federated analysis workflow. Active communication and engagement of several WP4 members in other CINECA work packages enabled the inclusion in this document of other aspects of the CINECA cohort data access model. Examples include the WP2 cohort survey, the Data Use Ontology framework that was adopted by WP3 and by WP1, and WP5 provided input on the harmonisation and formalisation of clinical use cases.

In this deliverable we considered trust as the extent to which one party is willing to depend on the other party in a given situation with a feeling of relative security, even though negative consequences are possible [1]. Such consideration is applicable in a series of circumstances evaluated in the report such as: cohort data sharing or model of data access described in paragraph in section 3.1 and 3.5, respectively.

The key findings reflect the project objectives listed in paragraph 2. In particular, the WP4 members have agreed on the use cases to focus on for the implementation of the federated analysis workflows. In addition, the use case identification has brought guidance on the selection of CINECA cohorts suitable for the WP4 federated analysis based on the data sharing levels and data access models described in this document. Finally, the following work informs the strategy to be used for implementing deliverable D4.2.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached:

- a) Description of different levels of data sharing and mapping of those levels to the cohorts available in CINECA.
- b) Identification of the use cases that will be implemented in (or possibly are dependent on) WP4, including the cohorts' data that will be used.
- c) Identification of existing models of data access that will be considered by WP4 in the subsequent tasks of the project.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Definition of data sharing

Level 1: Open access. Data sharing for research purposes can happen at multiple levels. In the simplest case, all data can be publicly shared on the Internet. This means that anybody can download the data and use it for their research. Additional limitations might be imposed by the **licence** under which the data is shared (i.e. preventing commercial use of the data), but there are no additional data protection or privacy requirements. Examples of human genetic datasets following the open access model are the 1000 Genomes Project [1], the CEDAR dataset [2], and the INSDC¹ exchange of publicly deposited nucleotide sequence data. However, because genetic data cannot be fully anonymised (it is possible to re-identify an individual if a small part of their or their close relative's genetic information is available from other sources [3]), the vast majority of human genetic and phenotypic datasets cannot be shared openly and are instead available under controlled access. Whether human genetic data can be shared openly or under a controlled access model is defined by the informed consent obtained from the research participants.

Level 2: Controlled access with download. The simplest model of controlled access data sharing is where the researchers, their home institution and data owners sign a data access agreement (DAA), after which the data can be transferred to the researcher's computing environment. This process is often managed by a Data Access Committee (DAC). The DAA usually describes the research project for which the data can be used as well as data security measures that need to be in place before the data can be downloaded and analysed. This model is predominantly used by datasets stored in repositories such as dbGaP², European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA)³, Japanese Genome-phenome Archive⁴, Synapse⁵ and some biobanks (e.g. Estonian Biobank).

Level 3: Controlled access without download. A more restrictive model of data sharing is where researchers are allowed to access the raw data after their data access agreement has been approved, but they can only do so in a pre-specified computing environment. Researchers can also analyse the data in the pre-specified environment, but they are not allowed to download or export the data to their own environment. Within CINECA, this model is followed by the BIOS and Psy(CoLauS) cohorts. For example, in the BIOS cohort, detailed phenotype and genotype data can currently only be accessed by using a virtual machine within the SurfSARA High Performance Computing private cloud, from where the data cannot be downloaded or exported⁶. Some types of data are also available for download at Level 2 via EGA, but this does not include the genotype data required for use case 3.5.1 described below.

Level 4: No access to individual-level data. The most restrictive model of data sharing is when the researcher is not allowed to see any individual-level data, but only 'anonymised' summary-level data. This is a common model for meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies (GWAS), where individual-level data is analysed in each cohort separately and only anonymised summary statistics

¹ <http://www.insdc.org/>

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap/>

³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ega/home>

⁴ <https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/jga/index-e.html>

⁵ <https://www.synapse.org/>

⁶ <https://www.bbmri.nl/acquisition-use-analyze/bios>

(effect sizes and p-values of genetic variants on trait of interest) are shared between cohorts (e.g. gnomAD⁷, GWAS catalog⁸, ClinVar⁹, AMP T2D knowledge portal¹⁰). This approach has also successfully been used for federated eQTL (expression Quantitative Trait Loci) meta-analysis [4,5]. Notably, even though some of the cohorts participating in the eQTL meta-analysis (Task 4.3.3) supported Level 2 or Level 3 access, Level 4 was chosen because it greatly simplified the data access procedure. However, whether summary-level data can be considered fully anonymised and can thus be shared publicly without risking re-identification of research participants remains an open question [6]. For example, if individual-level genotype data is available from other sources then it can be feasible to re-identify some individuals from GWAS summary statistics [7]. Thus, re-identification risks have to be carefully considered even when sharing summary-level data and appropriate measures should be implemented to mitigate those risks (e.g implementing the GA4GH ‘registered access’ model [8], limiting access to summary-level data to specific individuals, and deleting the data when they are no longer needed).

As more and more genetic and molecular data will be collected in the clinical setting, the demand for Level 3 and Level 4 data access is likely to increase in the future, examples include Genomics England that enables Level 3 access. Furthermore, translating data analysis workflows designed for Levels 1 and 2 to Levels 3 and 4 without sacrificing usability and requiring large amount of manual intervention is a key aim of CINECA WP4.

3.2. Data sharing in CINECA cohorts

An overview of the data sharing provided by the cohorts participating in CINECA is given in the [Milestone Document M2.1](#) of WP2 and the table below. Typically data access is valid for one year.

Cohort	Data Access Method	Access Level
CHILD	Download	2
H3Africa	Download	2
BIOS	Access via shared environment	3
Estonian Biobank	Download	2
(Psy)CoLaus	Download to an environment managed by SIB. Data cannot leave SIB.	3
UK biobank	Download but new data will be shared via cloud-based technology, still allowing download.	2

⁷ <https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/>

⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>

⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/>

¹⁰ <http://www.type2diabetesgenetics.org/>

EGA ¹¹	Datasets can be browsed with EGA public dataset catalog on EGA's website. Data access decision resides with the DACs. Datasets can be downloaded with a supported EGA client, detailed technical workflow for accessing data from EGA is described in D4.2 report (to be submitted). In seldom cases, data access could also be provided via temporary dropbox which may be accessed using Aspera or FTP.	2
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3.3 Existing models of data sharing outside CINECA

Below we outline examples of existing data access models that WP4 is taking into consideration, in order to develop a proposal for the federated analysis workflow framework that will be presented in the next WP4 deliverable D4.2.

The **dbGaP (Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes)**¹² is managed by NCBI and supports two modes of data access.

Full access allows an investigator to download the specific datasets once their request is approved (level 2). The process outline is as follows¹³:

- Investigator creates an *NIH eRA Commons account*, if not already registered.
- Investigator submits a *Data Access Request (DAR)* through the dbGaP portal. The necessary supporting information to be included in the DAR is described on dbGaP website and is quite extensive¹⁴.
- Completed DARs are forwarded first to the designated *Institutional Signed Official* and then to *Data Access Committee* for review;
- Once approved, the investigator downloads data with Aspera Connect software.

Another mode is **view only access** (level 3/4) for dbGaP Data Browser. In this scenario, an investigator only has to have an NIH eRA Commons account and to submit a simplified controlled-access application. Once approved, this grants a view only access (download is not possible) to a single aggregate dataset, *Compilation of Individual-Level Genomic Data for General Research Use* (study ID phs000688.v1.p1). It was constructed using individual-level genomic data designated for general research use with no further use limitations or restrictions — e. g., data use not requiring approval by an Institutional Review Board, having no publication embargo or other use limitations¹⁵. Using an online dbGaP data browser, an approved investigator can find and view discrete regions of a dbGaP genomic sequence dataset at nucleotide level resolution. It is possible to view aggregate variant data and individual genotypes, where available.

GEO (Gene Expression Omnibus)¹⁶ is an international public repository that archives and freely distributes microarray, next-generation sequencing, and other forms of high-throughput functional genomics data submitted by the research community. GEO database can be accessed at study-level

¹¹ <https://ega-archive.org/>

¹² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap/>

¹³ https://osp.od.nih.gov/wp-content/uploads/Extramural_Flowcharts_for_Data_Access.pdf

¹⁴ https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/projects/gap/cgi-bin/GetPdf.cgi?document_name=GeneralAAInstructions.pdf

¹⁵ https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/projects/gap/cgi-bin/collection.cgi?study_id=phs000688.v1.p1

¹⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>

where users can search for studies relevant to their interests (GEO DataSets) or at gene-level where users can search for gene expression profiles relevant to their interests (GEO Profiles).

Anybody can access and download public GEO data without any login requirements (level 1). Thus, all GEO records and raw data files are freely available through user-friendly mechanisms that allow users to query, locate, review and download studies and gene expression profiles of interest. GEO records may however remain private for a maximum of three years until a manuscript quoting the GEO accession number is made available to the public, though a journal publication is not a requirement for data submission to GEO. Private data is only accessible to the data submitters and reviewers once the records have been approved

There is a range of methods for performing simple or sophisticated queries of the GEO DataSets and GEO Profiles databases:

- Query and analyse directly from GEO site: Once the user have found a curated DataSet or Series of interest, there are several features available that help identify interesting gene expression profiles within that study. Curated DataSets include a find genes feature, cluster heatmaps and a t-test sample comparison tool.
- Downloading from the GEO FTP site: The user needs to enter a valid GEO accession number in the Accession Display bar to the list of current GEO repository contents or relevant data of their interests.
- Accessing programmatically: Users can take advantage of NCBI's Entrez programming utilities to access data stored in GEO DataSets and GEO Profiles. The 'Construct a URL' feature is a popular mechanism to download complete metadata records in bulk. Additionally, BioConductor users may be interested in the GEOquery package which parses GEO SOFT files for integration with BioConductor 'R' analysis resources.

3.4 Data Use Ontology (DUO)

DUO¹⁷ is an evolving effort to standardise data use conditions applicable for research data in the biomedical and genomics domain. Human subjects' datasets often have restrictions such as "available for cancer use" or "available for the study of paediatric diseases," deduced from the original biospecimen collection informed consent form, which must be respected when sharing and studying these datasets. Each institution uses unique language in their informed consent forms to describe secondary use restrictions and conditions. The aim of DUO is to allow DACs and researchers to interpret those conditions in a consistent, structured way. Its development is being led by GA4GH Driver Projects such as the EGA, where it is currently used in production¹⁸, Wellcome Sanger Institute, Broad Institute, Australian Genomics Health Alliance (AGHA), and Japan Agency for Medical Research and Development (AMED).

In the CINECA framework, after discussions with WP3, WP1 will be supporting Beacon 2.0 which will embed GA4GH DUO¹ for discovery of suitable cohorts—e.g. "show me all datasets that are allowed for cancer research". However, there are no concrete plans to integrate DUO to data access authorisation tools managed by DACs in WP2 at the moment. Actual assignment of DUO codes and matching of requests to cohort access will remain the manual responsibility of the Cohort DACs.

¹⁷<https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

¹⁸<https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001000002>

3.5 Use Cases

Use cases are practical examples that are based on the deliverables and tasks that the work packages have to achieve. They help capture the functional requirements needed to develop the federated analysis workflow and they serve as the basis for estimating, scheduling, and validating efforts. We present a brief description of the use cases that WP4 want to consider in the development of the federated analysis, explaining how the CINECA cohorts data access will be handled. Two use cases relevant to WP4 were identified.

The data needed to run those use cases will come from CINECA cohorts, meaning that the data access level of each cohort is an important dependency to take into account.

3.5.1 Federated eQTL Analysis

Expression Quantitative Trait Loci (eQTL) are genetic variants associated with changes in gene expression levels. There are generally two different types of eQTLs. *Cis* eQTLs are in close proximity to the regulated gene (+/- 1Mb) while *trans* eQTLs are separated by a larger distance (e.g. > 5Mb). The greater distance to the regulated gene usually makes the detection of *trans* eQTLs more difficult compared to the detection of *cis* eQTLs. However, the detection of *trans* eQTLs can be improved by using more and larger datasets.

This use case will facilitate a federated analysis of multiple datasets provided by multiple cohorts to discover both novel *cis* and *trans* eQTLs. It will be part of Deliverables D4.2 and D4.4, involving Tasks T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 (T4.3.1, T4.3.3) and utilising functionality developed by work packages WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP7 (see figure below).

Performing eQTL analysis requires genotype and gene expression data from matched set of individuals. Out of the seven CINECA cohorts described in Section 3.2, only BIOS, Estonian Biobank and CoLaus have matched gene expression and genotype data available and only BIOS and Estonian Biobank have profiled gene expression in the same tissue (whole blood). Thus, we have decided to perform federated *cis* and *trans* eQTL analysis using the data from the BIOS and Estonian Biobank cohorts. Although, the Estonian Biobank data can be downloaded locally (level 2), the data access procedure can be complicated and time consuming. Furthermore, the genetic data from the BIOS cohort can only be analysed in the computational environment controlled by UMCG (level 3). Thus, we plan to perform federated eQTL analysis at level 4, where no individual-level data is exchanged between cohorts. Instead, we will perform an independent analysis in each cohort separately and subsequently we will use statistical meta-analysis to combine the results. We are considering both standard weighted Z-score meta-analysis [5] as well as the HASE framework [9]. Additional advantage of Level 4 data access is that the same analysis can later be expanded to additional cohorts part of the eQTLGen Consortium, many of which only allow Level 4 data access [4].

Figure 1: Diagram showing work package dependencies and requirements related to the Federated eQTL Analysis use case.

3.5.2 Polygenic Risk Score Analysis

A Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) is an estimate of an individual’s propensity to a phenotype, given a set of genotypes. PRS are among other factors used to estimate future susceptibility for particular diseases such as coronary artery disease, type 2 diabetes and ischaemic stroke [10,11]. Similar to eQTLs, the determination of a PRS can be improved by using more and larger datasets.

The PRS use case proposed here is a simple PRS across two (or more) sample sets from a similar ethnic background. After performing a PRS workflow, the information obtained from the original sample set can be utilised and shared for wider analyses. However, the individual level data of all participating sample sets will not be shared, as exemplified by data sharing levels 3 and 4. This though does not preclude the use of the PRS workflow with data more freely available such as those with data sharing levels 1 and 2 as well as with the use of summary level statistics.

The PRS is generated in an initial cohort and the list of variants, that comprise the PRS, and a phenotype to be tested are shared with the second cohort for testing. This method fits well with all levels of data sharing as the results returned by the workflow from the second sample set would be of a summary nature [10] such as p values from association testing under the null hypothesis, effect estimates, AUC, or phenotypic variance explained, this being dependant on the analysis method used and the overall aim of the analysis. This ensures that any data returned for the wider analyses are not personally identifiable and so can be more widely shared without compromising privacy.

This use case will facilitate a federated analysis of multiple datasets provided by multiple cohorts such as the Estonian and UK Biobanks as well as some of those present in EGA. It will be part of

Deliverables D4.2, D4.3 and D4.4, involving Tasks T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 (T4.3.1, T4.3.2) and utilising functionality developed by work packages WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP7 (see figure below).

Figure 2: Diagram showing work package dependencies and requirements related to the Polygenic Risk Score use case.

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5. Abbreviations

AUC	Area Under the Curve
DAC	Data Access Committee
DAR	Data Access Request
dbGaP	Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
eQTL	Expression Quantitative Trait Loci
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GEO	Gene Expression Omnibus
PRS	Polygenic Risk Score
WP	Work Package

